

Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 26- and 28-membered tetraazamacrocycles

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Abstract : 2+2 Cyclocondensation of 2,3-hexanedione with 1,9-diaminononane or 1,10-diaminodecane in the presence of metal ions as templates resulted in the formation of complexes of the types [ML(NO₃)₂]NO₃ {M = Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}}, [ML(NO₃)₂] {M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}}, [CuL]Cl₂ and [ZnLCl₂] (where L = tetraazamacrocycle having 26- or 28-membered ring). These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductances, magnetic measurements and IR, electronic and mass spectra. Zn^{II} complex has been characterized by NMR spectrum also.

Keywords : Macrocycles, transition metal, 2,3-hexanedione, 1,9-diaminononane, 1,10-diaminodecane.

In continuation of our earlier work on metal complexes of tetraazamacrocycles¹, in the present communication, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 26- and 28-membered tetraazamacrocycles derived from 2,3-hexanedione and 1,9-diaminononane or 1,10-diaminodecane are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of metal salts with 2,3-hexanedione and 1,9-diaminononane or 1,10-diaminodecane in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios result in the formation of complexes of 26- or 28-membered tetraazamacrocycles (Scheme 1).

The resulting macrocyclic complexes have 12- or 13-membered chelate rings which are not improbable due to the flexibility of the ring and have been reported earlier in case of the complexes of long chain flexible bidentate ligands such as Co^{III} complexes of 1,ω-diaminoalkanes H₂N(CH₂)_nNH₂ (n = 2-14)² and platinum and palladium complexes of diphosphines Bu^t₂P(CH₂)_nPBu^t₂ (n = 9, 10 or 12)³. Moreover, such chelate rings would be more stable in metal complexes of macrocyclic ligands since macrocyclic complexes are often stabilized to a greater extent by the macrocyclic effect "multiple juxtapositional fixedness"⁴.

The resulting macrocyclic complexes are coloured solids and stable at room temperature. On heating these do not melt but decompose. These are insoluble in carbon tetrachloride, methanol, chloroform and acetonitrile but soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide. The analyses and characteristics of the complexes are given in Table 1.

(1)

n = 9 (L¹), 10 (L²)

M	X	k	m	x
Cr	NO ₃	3	1	9
Fe	NO ₃	3	1	9
Co	NO ₃	2	0	6
Ni	NO ₃	2	0	6
Cu	Cl	2	2	2
Zn	Cl	2	0	0

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

Eggleston and Jackels⁵ have ruled out the possibility of the formation of 1 + 1 condensation products, such as

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of tetraazamacrocyclic complexes^a

Compd. Colour (yield %)	Decomp temp (°C)	Metal (%) : Found (Calcd.)	Cond. (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (B M)	Bands (cm ⁻¹) Transition
[CrL ¹ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ Grey (46)	230-232	7.42 (7.31)	115	4.09	16530 (⁴ B _{1g} → ⁴ E _g (a)) 25000 (⁴ B _{1g} → ⁴ E _g (b)/ ⁴ B _{2g}) 27100 (⁴ B _{1g} → ⁴ A _{2g})
[CrL ² (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ Grey (46)	162	6.91 (7.03)	107	3.91	16530 (⁴ B _{1g} → ⁴ E _g (a)) 25000 (⁴ B _{1g} → ⁴ E _g (b)/ ⁴ B _{2g}) 27100 (⁴ B _{1g} → ⁴ A _{2g})
[FeL ¹ (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ Brown (40)	122-124	7.72 (7.81)	105	6.45	13700 (⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (G)) 16400 (⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g}) 25000 (⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (D))
[FeL ² (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ Brown (46)	131	7.61 (7.51)	95	6.54	13700 (⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (G)) 16400 (⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g}) 25000 (⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (D))
[CoL ¹ (NO ₃) ₂] Green (42)	182-183	9.10 (8.98)	82	4.92	11000 (⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g}) 16400 (⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ A _{2g}) 18500 (⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P))
[CoL ² (NO ₃) ₂] Green (42)	172	8.74 (8.61)	69	5.04	11000 (⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g}) 16400 (⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ A _{2g}) 18500 (⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P))
[NiL ¹ (NO ₃) ₂] Green (40)	198-200	9.04 (8.95)	84	4.03	9850 (³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{2g}) 16400 (³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (F)) 27000 (³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (P))
[NiL ² (NO ₃) ₂] Green (47)	149-151	8.44 (8.58)	62	4.40	9850 (³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{2g}) 16400 (³ A _{1g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (F)) 27000 (³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (P))
[CuL ¹]Cl ₂ Green (43)	109-110	10.37 (10.46)	60	2.26	16400 (Ligand field transition)
[CuL ²]Cl ₂ Green (42)	148	10.02 (10.00)	66	2.24	16400 (Ligand field transition)
[ZnL ¹]Cl ₂ White (58)	215	10.85 (10.73)	17	Diamag.	-
[ZnL ²]Cl ₂ White (47)	222-224	10.38 (10.26)	15	Diamag.	-

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory N and Cl analyses and show charge transfer bands at 29400 cm⁻¹.

diazepine, during the template synthesis of Fe^{II}, Co^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes of 2,9-dimethyl-3,10-diphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene (MePhTIM), on the basis of ¹H NMR studies and the possibility of *cis*-isomer on the basis of ¹³C NMR studies.

In the IR spectra of the macrocyclic complexes, no absorption band was observed at 1700 and 3200-3400 cm⁻¹ indicating the absence of unreacted >C=O or -NH₂ group⁶. Thus >C=O and -NH₂ groups have con-

ditioned to give C=N linkage. All the complexes synthesized during the present investigations show strong absorption bands in the region 1580-1630 cm⁻¹ which can be attributed to the coordinated >C=N group. For [Cu(MePhTIM)]²⁺, it has been reported that ν(C=N)_{sym} and ν(C=N)_{asym} bands are in the region 1585-1595 and 1602-1612 cm⁻¹⁷. All the macrocyclic complexes containing nitrate exhibit absorption bands at 810-830 and ~1380 cm⁻¹ due to ionic nitrate⁸ while the bands at 1010-1040 and 1460-1550 cm⁻¹ are due to coordinated

nitrate group behaving as a monodentate ligand⁹. In the IR spectra of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, appearance of absorption bands due to coordinated as well as ionic nitrate indicates that the nitrate groups are weakly coordinated.

Molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO are recorded in Table 1. The Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes behave as 3 : 1 electrolytes indicating that the solvent molecules replace the coordinated nitrate groups. Molar conductances of ~109 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in DMSO have been reported for 3 : 1 electrolytes¹⁰. The conductance values for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes correspond to 2 : 1 electrolytes indicating that nitrate groups are replaced by solvent molecules¹¹. Cu^{II} complexes behave as 2 : 1 electrolytes. The molar conductances of Zn^{II} complexes are very low showing them to be non-electrolytes. The μ_{eff} values and the bands observed in the electronic spectra of the complexes along with their assignments are given in Table 1.

¹H NMR spectrum of one representative Zn^{II} complex (2) has been recorded. The α-CH₂ protons of the amine residue give a triplet at δ 2.68 ppm due to coupling with the β-CH₂ protons. The β-CH₂ protons of the amine residue give a broad peak at δ 1.55 ppm. The remaining methylene protons (γ and others) of the amine

residue give rise to a broad peak at δ 1.30 ppm. In macrocyclic precursor, 1,2,8,9-tetraphenyl-3,7-diazaduohepta-2,7-diene-1,9-dione (KIM, 3) the α-CH₂ protons have been reported to appear as a triplet at δ 3.63 ppm and β-

[Mass Spectrum]
 Date : 14-Sep-2005 10:46
 Sample: RNP-MM-41 DR R N PRASAD JAIPUR #8085
 Note : -
 Inlet : Direct Ion Mode : FAB+
 Spectrum Type : Normal Ion [MF-Linear]
 RT : 1.22 min Scan# : (6,17)
 BP : m/z 201.0000 Int. : 8.98
 Output m/z range : 97.2552 to 1016.9139 Cut Level : 0.00 %

Fig. 1. Mass spectrum of [ZnL₂Cl₂].

CH₂ protons as a quintet at δ 2.11 ppm¹².

The free macrocycle has not been isolated during the present investigations but it is expected to exhibit the α - and β -CH₂ protons almost at the same position as reported for KIM. As compared to KIM, in Zn^{II} complex of the macrocycle these peaks are observed at higher field. This high field shifting of these protons confirms the coordination of the nitrogen atom of the macrocycle to the zinc atom. The CH₃^(a) protons of the ketone residue give rise to a triplet at δ 0.91 ppm due to coupling with the CH₂^(b) protons and CH₂^(c) protons give a broad peak at δ 2.12 ppm. The CH₃^(d) protons give rise to a singlet at δ 1.85 ppm. The peaks due to CH₂^(b) protons of the ketone residue merge with the peaks of CH₂ (β and others) protons of the amine residue. Thus the ¹H NMR data confirm the proposed structure of the complex.

The FAB mass spectra of Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of the macrocycle have been recorded using NBA matrix. All the spectra exhibit peaks due to molecular ions [M⁺] and free macrocycle [L⁺]. This confirms the formation of the macrocyclic complexes. In few complexes peaks due to [M+H]⁺ have also been observed¹³. In addition to the peaks due to the molecular ions and the free macrocycles, the spectra exhibit peaks assignable to various fragments arising from the thermal cleavage of the macrocycle and its complexes. The mass spectrum of Zn^{II} complex is reproduced in Fig. 1 and its fragmentation pattern is given in Scheme 2. The complex shows a molecular ion peak at m/z 634 (8.3%). Fragment (b) is formed due to the loss of two chlorine atoms from the molecular ion (a) and appears at m/z 564 (7.7%). There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of the complex.

Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of [ZnL₂Cl₂].

(A) In this pathway the metal ion remains attached with the macrocyclic framework and step by step loss of two propyl groups and two methyl groups from (b) gives peaks at m/z 521 (13.8%), 478 (16.6%), 463 (6.6%) and 448 (8.3%) due to the species (c), (d), (e) and (f) respectively. Loss of Zn atom from the species (f) finally gives the species (k).

(B) In this pathway the metal ion may be lost in the beginning and a peak at m/z 500 (8.8%) appears due to the free macrocycle (g). Subsequent loss of two propyl groups and two methyl groups from the macrocycle gives peaks at m/z 457 (11.1%), 414 (16.6%), 399 (8.3%) and 384 (8.3%) due to the species (h), (i), (j) and (k) respectively¹⁴.

Experimental

$\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ZnCl_2 (all Fluka), $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck), $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B.D.H.), 2,3-hexanedione (Aldrich), 1,9-diaminononane (Merck) and 1,10-diaminodecane (Fluka) were used as supplied. *n*-Butanol was distilled before use.

Chromium was determined volumetrically by potassium dichromate using diphenylamine as indicator. Similarly, iron content was determined in Fe^{III} complexes as Fe^{II} after its reduction with stannous chloride. Copper was determined iodometrically. Iodine liberated was titrated against sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator. Cobalt, nickel and zinc were determined volumetrically by EDTA using xylenol orange indicator for cobalt and Eriochrome black T for nickel and zinc. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Chlorine was determined gravimetrically as AgCl . IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT-IR spectrophotometer in the region $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Molar conductances of the complexes were measured at room temperature on a Systronics direct reading conductivity meter 304 using 10^{-3} M solutions in DMSO. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature (300 K) on a Gouy balance at Banasthali Vidyapith, Banasthali, Rajasthan, using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as calibrant. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Jasco-7800 UV-VIS spectrophotometer at Mohan Lal Sukhadia University, Udaipur. ^1H NMR spectrum ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) was recorded on a Bruker-300 NMR spectrometer using TMS

as a reference at Biocryst Pharmaceutical Inc., Birmingham, Alabama (USA). The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes : $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.0 mmol) was dissolved in $\sim 20\text{ ml}$ *n*-butanol with stirring and 2.0 mmol of 2,3-hexanedione (in $\sim 15\text{ ml}$ of *n*-butanol) was added. A solution of 1,9-diaminononane or 1,10-diaminodecane (2.0 mmol in $\sim 15\text{ ml}$ of *n*-butanol) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The stirring was continued for $\sim 5\text{ h}$. The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Reactions of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and ZnCl_2 with 2,3-hexanedione and 1,9-diaminononane or 1,10-diaminodecane were carried out using similar procedure and the corresponding complexes were isolated. The analyses and the characteristics of the complexes are given in Table 1.

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